

Impact of Chronic Alcohol Consumption on Hematological Parameters: Evidence from a Kolkata Laboratory-Based StudyUjjwal Bandyopadhyay¹, Supti Mukhopadhyay (Banerjee)²¹Professor & Head, Department of Psychiatry, ESIPGIMSR and ESIC Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata²Senior Consultant Pathologist, Associate Professor, Department of Pathology ICARE Institute of Medical Science and Research, Haldia, Proprietor - Rishi Pathological Laboratory, Kolkata

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Abstract**Background:** Chronic alcohol consumption has significant effects on the hematopoietic system, often leading to various hematological abnormalities. Early identification of these changes can help prevent long-term complications and guide clinical intervention.**Objectives:** To evaluate the hematological alterations in patients with chronic alcohol abuse and to assess the correlation between duration of alcohol intake and specific hematological parameters.**Methods:** This was an observational cross-sectional study conducted over a period of one year at Rishi Pathological Laboratory, Kolkata. A total of 30 adult patients with a history of alcohol use for more than one year were included. Hematological parameters including hemoglobin, total and differential leukocyte count, platelet count, MCV, MCH, and MCHC were measured using an automated hematology analyzer. Statistical analysis was performed to evaluate the frequency of abnormalities and their correlation with alcohol use duration.**Results:** Anemia was present in 73.3% of participants, with 70% showing macrocytosis (elevated MCV). Thrombocytopenia was noted in 36.7% of cases. A significant negative correlation was found between alcohol duration and hemoglobin ($r = -0.56$, $p = 0.002$) and platelet count ($r = -0.48$, $p = 0.009$), while MCV showed a strong positive correlation ($r = +0.61$, $p < 0.001$).**Conclusion:** Chronic alcohol abuse is strongly associated with hematological abnormalities, particularly anemia, macrocytosis, and thrombocytopenia. Routine hematological screening can serve as an important tool in identifying early systemic effects of alcohol toxicity.**Keywords:** Alcohol abuse, Hematological changes, Anemia, Macrocytosis, Thrombocytopenia, MCV, Platelet count, Chronic alcoholism.

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Introduction

Alcohol abuse, which refers to the harmful or hazardous use of alcoholic beverages, is a serious and escalating global public health issue. It encompasses a spectrum of excessive drinking behaviors that can lead to health, social, and psychological consequences. Chronic alcohol consumption not only affects the central nervous system and liver but also exerts significant systemic toxicity, particularly on the hematopoietic system. Alcohol-induced hematological changes arise through multiple mechanisms, including direct bone marrow suppression, nutritional deficiencies (especially folate and vitamin B12), alcohol-related liver dysfunction leading to impaired hematopoiesis, and alterations in immune function and cytokine regulation [1]. These pathophysiological processes result in measurable changes in complete blood count parameters, often

detectable before clinical symptoms arise. Globally, alcohol consumption is ranked as the seventh leading risk factor contributing to death and disability, affecting millions of individuals annually. The Global Burden of Disease Study (2019) estimates that alcohol use accounts for more than 2.4 million deaths each year, with the most pronounced burden observed in the 15–49-year age group—an economically productive segment of the population [2]. The associated morbidity is not limited to liver disease or neuropsychiatric disorders; a wide range of hematological abnormalities has also been documented. These include normocytic and macrocytic anemia, thrombocytopenia, neutropenia, and pancytopenia in severe cases. One of the hallmark findings in alcohol-related hematologic toxicity is macrocytosis, which often presents in the absence

of anemia and may serve as an early laboratory indicator of chronic alcohol intake [3].

In the Indian context, alcohol consumption patterns have undergone a significant transformation over the past decade. With rising socioeconomic changes, increased urbanization, and evolving cultural norms, the prevalence of alcohol use has steadily increased, particularly among younger adults. According to the National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), approximately 18.8% of Indian men and 1.3% of women consume alcohol, with significantly higher figures reported in certain regions. Eastern states like West Bengal show a relatively higher prevalence of alcohol use compared to the national average [4]. However, the health impacts of this trend are often under-recognized, especially in relation to hematological disorders. The clinical manifestations of alcohol-related hematological abnormalities are frequently overlooked or misattributed to other causes, leading to underdiagnosis and delayed management [5].

Furthermore, hematological investigations are rarely prioritized in the routine work-up of alcohol-dependent individuals unless overt symptoms appear. This diagnostic gap persists despite evidence that complete blood count parameters—being inexpensive, accessible, and non-invasive—can provide crucial insight into systemic alcohol toxicity. Macrocytic anemia, elevated mean corpuscular volume (MCV), thrombocytopenia, and leukopenia are all well-documented yet underutilized markers in the evaluation of chronic alcohol users [6].

Given the limited number of focused studies on alcohol-related hematological changes in India, particularly in eastern regions like West Bengal, there is a pressing need to generate region-specific data. Local laboratories and clinical centers can play a vital role in identifying population-specific trends that may guide preventive healthcare measures.

Therefore, this study has been undertaken at Rishi Pathological Laboratory, Kolkata, to evaluate the changes in hematological parameters among patients with a history of chronic alcohol abuse over a one-year period. The study aims to highlight the common patterns of hematological derangements associated with long-term alcohol consumption and to assess their potential clinical implications. Through this, the study intends to contribute valuable evidence toward early diagnosis, risk stratification, and targeted intervention for individuals affected by alcohol-related systemic toxicity [7].

Aims and Objectives

This study aims to assess the changes in hematological parameters among patients with

chronic alcohol abuse. It seeks to identify common abnormalities such as anemia, leukopenia, thrombocytopenia, and altered red cell indices, and to explore any correlation between the duration of alcohol intake and the degree of hematological changes.

Materials and Methodology

This observational cross-sectional study was conducted over a period of one year at Rishi Pathological Laboratory, Kolkata, with the aim of assessing changes in hematological parameters among patients with chronic alcohol abuse, during which eligible patients attending the laboratory were screened and enrolled based on predefined criteria.

The study population consisted of adult patients aged 18 years and above with a self-reported or documented history of chronic alcohol consumption for more than one year. Participants were included after obtaining written informed consent. Patients with a history of known hematological disorders, recent blood transfusions within the last three months, chronic systemic illnesses such as liver cirrhosis, chronic kidney disease, tuberculosis, malignancies, or any other condition known to affect hematological parameters were excluded from the study to avoid confounding results. Those who were not willing to participate were also excluded.

A total of 30 participants were included in the study based on purposive sampling, where patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria were selected consecutively as they presented during the study period. After confirming eligibility, a detailed clinical history was obtained from each participant with emphasis on alcohol intake habits including frequency, quantity, and duration of consumption.

Venous blood samples were collected from each participant under strict aseptic precautions in EDTA vials for hematological examination. The collected samples were processed on a fully automated hematology analyzer available at the laboratory.

The parameters assessed included hemoglobin concentration, total leukocyte count (TLC), differential leukocyte count (DLC), platelet count, and red cell indices such as mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), and mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC). The analyzer was calibrated regularly according to the manufacturer's instructions to ensure accuracy and reliability of results. The data obtained were compiled using Microsoft Excel and analyzed using standard statistical software. Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, and percentage were used to present the findings. Correlation tests were applied to assess the association between the

duration of alcohol consumption and changes in hematological parameters. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant for all analyses.

Result

In this cross-sectional study of 30 patients with chronic alcohol abuse, the majority were males (90%) and belonged to the age group of 31–50 years. Most participants (43.3%) reported consuming more than 180 mL of alcohol daily, and 50% had a history of alcohol use for more than 6 years. Country-made liquor was the most commonly consumed type of alcohol (63.3%). Hematological analysis revealed that 73.3% of participants were anemic, with 40% having hemoglobin levels below 10 g/dL. Macrocytosis (MCV > 100 fL) was present in 70% of the study population, with a mean MCV of 104.2 ± 8.5 fL. Elevated MCH levels were noted in 60% of

subjects, while low MCHC was observed in 30%. Thrombocytopenia (platelet count < 1.5 lakh/mm³) was present in 36.7% of cases, and leukocyte abnormalities were seen in a minority of participants (13.3% with elevated WBC count and 6.7% with leukopenia). Statistical analysis showed a significant inverse correlation between the duration of alcohol use and hemoglobin ($r = -0.56$, $p = 0.002$) as well as platelet count ($r = -0.48$, $p = 0.009$), indicating progressive bone marrow suppression with prolonged alcohol exposure.

A strong positive correlation was found between alcohol use duration and MCV ($r = +0.61$, $p < 0.001$), reinforcing the association between chronic alcohol intake and macrocytosis. These findings underscore the hematotoxic effects of long-term alcohol abuse and highlight the utility of routine hematological parameters as early indicators of alcohol-related systemic damage.

Table 1: Demographic Profile and Alcohol Use History of Study Participants (n = 30)

Variable	Category	Number (%)
Age Group (years)	18–30	6 (20.0%)
	31–40	9 (30.0%)
	41–50	10 (33.3%)
	>50	5 (16.7%)
Gender	Male	27 (90.0%)
	Female	3 (10.0%)
Duration of Alcohol Use	1–3 years	6 (20.0%)
	4–6 years	9 (30.0%)
	7–10 years	8 (26.7%)
	>10 years	7 (23.3%)
Average Daily Intake	<90 mL	4 (13.3%)
	90–180 mL	13 (43.3%)
	>180 mL	13 (43.3%)
Type of Alcohol Consumed	Country-made liquor	19 (63.3%)
	Branded spirits (whisky, rum)	11 (36.7%)

Table 2: Hematological Abnormalities Among Study Participants (n = 30)

Parameter	Normal Range	Mean \pm SD	Abnormal Cases n (%)
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	13.0–17.0 (M)	11.2 ± 2.1	22 (73.3%) – low
	12.0–15.0 (F)		
Total WBC count (/mm ³)	4000–11000	8300 ± 2150	4 (13.3%) – high, 2 (6.7%) – low
Platelet count (/mm ³)	1.5–4.5 lakh	1.72 ± 0.64 lakh	11 (36.7%) – low
MCV (fL)	80–100	104.2 ± 8.5	21 (70.0%) – high (macrocytosis)
MCH (pg)	27–32	33.1 ± 2.4	18 (60.0%) – high
MCHC (%)	32–36	31.8 ± 1.9	9 (30.0%) – low

Table 3: Correlation Between Duration of Alcohol Use and Hematological Parameters (n = 30)

Hematological Parameter	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value	Interpretation
Hemoglobin	-0.56	0.002	Significant inverse correlation
Platelet Count	-0.48	0.009	Moderate negative correlation
MCV	+0.61	<0.001	Strong positive correlation
MCH	+0.53	0.003	Moderate positive correlation
WBC Count	+0.11	0.542	No significant correlation

Figure 1: Distribution of study Participants According to haemoglobin Levels

Discussion

This study evaluated hematological alterations among patients with chronic alcohol abuse and demonstrated a significant burden of abnormalities, including anemia, macrocytosis, thrombocytopenia, and altered red cell indices.

In the present study, anemia was found in 73.3% of the participants, with 40% having hemoglobin levels below 10 g/dL. These findings are consistent with the study by Agrawal et al., who reported a 69% prevalence of anemia among alcohol-dependent individuals in a tertiary care setting in India [8]. Chronic alcohol consumption leads to poor nutritional intake, especially folate and vitamin B12 deficiency, along with bone marrow suppression, contributing to anemia. Similar results were documented in a study by Dasgupta et al., where 64.5% of alcoholics had low hemoglobin levels, emphasizing anemia as one of the earliest hematological effects of alcohol abuse [9].

The mean corpuscular volume (MCV) was elevated in 70% of subjects in this study, with a mean of 104.2 ± 8.5 fL. Macrocytosis, even in the absence of anemia, is often a hallmark of chronic alcohol intake. The pathogenesis is believed to involve impaired DNA synthesis due to folate deficiency, direct toxicity of alcohol on erythroid precursors, and lipid alteration of red cell membranes [10]. A similar frequency of macrocytosis (72%) was noted in a study conducted by Rao and Kiran at a pathology lab in Andhra Pradesh, reinforcing its diagnostic value in suspected alcohol-related hematological changes [11].

Thrombocytopenia was observed in 36.7% of cases in the current study, which aligns with previous findings. Chronic alcohol use causes suppression of megakaryocytes, immune-mediated platelet destruction, and hypersplenism in advanced cases. In a study by Mukherjee et al., 38% of chronic alcohol users had platelet counts below 1.5 lakh/mm³ [12]. These alterations increase the risk of bleeding complications, especially in trauma or surgical settings.

A significant inverse correlation was observed between the duration of alcohol use and hemoglobin levels ($r = -0.56$, $p = 0.002$) and platelet counts ($r = -0.48$, $p = 0.009$) in this study, while a positive correlation existed with MCV ($r = +0.61$, $p < 0.001$). These findings suggest a dose-dependent hematotoxic effect of alcohol over time. In support, Thomas et al. reported similar trends, where the duration and amount of alcohol intake were predictive of macrocytosis and anemia severity [13].

Additionally, MCH was found to be elevated in 60% of patients, which is commonly seen in alcohol-related macrocytic anemias. However, the MCHC values were mostly within or slightly below the normal range, consistent with previous literature showing alcohol-induced anisocytosis without major impact on hemoglobin concentration per cell [14].

Overall, this study reinforces the role of complete blood count (CBC) as a valuable, low-cost tool in identifying early systemic effects of alcohol abuse. Regular monitoring of hematological parameters

can aid in early intervention, especially in primary and secondary care settings.

Conclusion

The present study highlights that chronic alcohol abuse is significantly associated with various hematological abnormalities, most notably anemia, macrocytosis, and thrombocytopenia. A strong correlation was observed between the duration of alcohol consumption and derangements in red cell indices and platelet counts, suggesting a dose-dependent hematotoxic effect. Routine evaluation of hematological parameters in individuals with chronic alcohol use can serve as an important diagnostic and prognostic tool, enabling early detection of systemic complications. These findings underscore the need for regular blood screening and timely clinical intervention in alcohol-dependent individuals to prevent long-term morbidity.

Limitations

This study had a few limitations that must be acknowledged. Firstly, the sample size was relatively small ($n=30$), which may limit the generalizability of the findings to the broader population. Secondly, the study relied on self-reported alcohol intake history, which is subject to recall bias and underreporting due to social stigma. Detailed quantification of alcohol types and exact daily intake could not be standardized.

Furthermore, confounding factors such as nutritional deficiencies, liver function status, and co-existing infections were not fully assessed, which could also contribute to hematological changes. Lastly, being a single-center study conducted at a diagnostic laboratory, the findings may not reflect trends in community-based or hospital-admitted populations.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that complete blood count (CBC) testing should be routinely incorporated into the evaluation of individuals with chronic alcohol abuse, even in the absence of overt clinical symptoms. Health professionals should be sensitized to consider macrocytosis and unexplained anemia as potential indicators of alcohol-related hematological toxicity. Larger, multicenter studies incorporating nutritional, hepatic, and biochemical parameters are warranted to better delineate the spectrum and mechanisms of alcohol-induced blood abnormalities. Public health strategies should also focus on awareness, screening, and early referral for alcohol-dependent

individuals to prevent hematological and systemic complications.

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